

ON THE ALKALOID ISOLATED FROM THE MATURED BARK OF *AEGLE MARMELOS*, CORREA

By K. K. CHAKRAVARTY

The alkaloid, isolated from the matured bark of *Aegle marmelos* (Bihar variety), has been proved to be identical with γ -fagarine, an alkaloid isolated by Stuckert and his collaborators from the leaves of *Fagara Coco*.

From the matured bark of *Aegle marmelos* (Bihar variety) Mookerjee (*Current Science*, 1943, 12, 209) isolated three crystalline constituents, one of which is an alkaloid m.p. 142°, the other two substances being neutral.

In the present communication is discussed the constitution of this alkaloid which has been named "aegelenin."

The alkaloid melts at 142° and is obtained in a yield of 0.3 per cent. It is fairly soluble in acetone, chloroform, sparingly in ether, ethyl acetate and alcohol and in petroleum ether and water. A solution of the base in alcohol is neutral to litmus and it is optically inactive. It does not contain any solvent of crystallisation. It does not produce any colouration with ferric chloride in alcohol but gives the following colour reactions :

TABLE I

Reagent.	...	Colour.
1. Conc. sulphuric acid	...	Colourless
2. Conc. nitric acid	...	Yellow
3. Frohde's reagent	...	Greenish yellow
4. Erdmann's reagent	...	Greenish yellow
5. Mandelin's reagent	...	Pale red to deep red.

It dissolves freely in acids and gives an orange precipitate with Dragendorff's reagent and a chocolate brown precipitate with a solution of iodine in potassium iodide. It is a monoacid base, forms a deep yellow picrate and an orange chloroplatinate, both of which are crystalline.

The analyses of the base and its salts indicate the formula $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N$ which has been supported by the molecular weight data. The N-methyl determination (Herzig and Meyer, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 319; *Monatsh.*, 1894, 15, 613; *ibid.*, 1897, 18, 382) and Gaebel's test for methylenedioxy group (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1910, 248, 207) are negative but the presence of two methoxyl groups by the method of Zeisel-Pregl-Vieböck (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2881, 3207; *Monatsh.*, 1885, 6, 989; 1886, 7, 406) could be established. The base does not form any acetyl or benzoyl derivative thus suggesting the tertiary nature of the basic nitrogen atom.

TABLE II

<i>Aegelenin</i> m. p. 142°	γ -Fagarine m. p. 142°	<i>Aegelenin</i>	γ -Fagarine
Molecular formula $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N$	Molecular formula $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N$	<i>Degradation products</i>	
<i>Picrate</i> ($C_{13}H_{11}O_3N$ $C_6H_3O_7N_3$) m. p. 176°	m. p. 177°	(b) Acid ($C_{12}H_{11}O_3N$)	m. p. 215° (decomp.)
<i>Degradation products</i> (a) Aldehyde ($C_{12}H_{11}O_3N$)	185° (decomp.)	(c) Decarboxylation product of (b) ($C_{10}H_9O_3N$)	248° (decomp.)
<i>Phenylhydrazone of (a)</i> ($C_{18}H_{17}O_3N_3$)	205° (decomp.)	(d) Nitroso derivative of (c)	216° (decomp.)
	207° (decomp.)		248° (decomp.)

These properties agree with those of γ -fagarine, isolated from the leaves of *Fagara coco* (Stuckert and his collaborators, *Investigaciones del Laboratorio de Quimica Biologica Cordoba, Argentina*, Vol. I, 1933 and Vol. II, 1938; Denlofeu, Labriola and Laughe, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2326).

As an authentic specimen of γ -fagarine could not be procured, the alkaloid was further degraded to the aldehyde and the acid and their properties compared with the corresponding products obtained from γ -fagarine.

The data presented in the Table II do not leave any doubt that the alkaloid of *Aegle marmelos* is identical with γ -fagarine.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of γ -Fagarine.—Matured bark of *Aegle marmelos* (400 g.), collected from Bihar in the month of October, was dried in the sun, coarsely powdered and extracted with ether in a Soxhlet for 48 hours. The deep brown ethereal extract was digested with 0.1% hydrochloric acid (200 c.c. in instalments). The extraction was continued till the acid digest gave insignificant precipitate with Dragendorff's reagent. Four to five extractions were sufficient for the complete extraction of the base. The red acid aqueous solution was cooled in ice and basified with sodium bicarbonate. The base separating in flocks was taken up in ether (300 c.c.). The pale yellow ethereal extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled. The solid residue (1.2 g.), left on removal of ether, crystallised from ethyl acetate in colourless prisms, m.p. 142°. On repeated crystallisations from ethyl acetate, alcohol, and acetone, the m.p. could not be raised. There was no loss in weight when the crystals were dried *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 100°. (Found: C, 68.41; H, 4.85; N, 6.2; OMe, 27.22; Mol. wt. 227. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N$: C, 68.12; H, 4.8; N, 6.11; OMe 27.07 per cent. Mol. wt., 229).

Chloroplatinate.—To a cooled solution of the base (0.2 g.), dissolved in hydrochloric acid, platinum chloride solution (5%) was slowly added, till precipitation was complete. The orange flocculent precipitate was collected, washed with cold water containing a few drops of hydrochloric acid and crystallised from water acidulated with hydrochloric acid. The orange needles, thus obtained, decomposed on heating above 200° without melting. [Found in a dry sample: Pt, 22.52. $(C_{13}H_{11}O_3N)_2H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 22.47 per cent].

The picrate of the base was prepared by adding picric acid solution to an alcoholic solution of the base. The crystals which separated on cooling were collected, washed with cold alcohol and crystallised from the same solvent. The yellow needles of the picrate melted at 175° (decomp.). On further crystallisation from other solvents there was no change in m.p. [Found in a sample dried *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 at 100° for 4 hours: N, 12.50. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N, C_6H_2(OH)(NO_2)_3$: N, 12.22 per cent].

Oxidation of the Base with Potassium Permanganate.—A solution of the base (0.5 g.) in acetone (30 c.c.) was gently boiled on a water-bath and a neutral solution of potassium permanganate (1.0 g. in 20 c.c. acetone) was added. The solution was then refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, cooled and filtered. The manganese dioxide residue (A) was thoroughly washed with boiling acetone. The pale yellow filtrate (B) was worked up as follows:

Isolation of γ -Fagaric Aldehyde.—The filtrate (B) was freed from the solvent and the residue was digested with an aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate and filtered. The filtrate (C) was added to the manganese dioxide residue (*vide supra*) and the mixture was subsequently worked up for the acid (*vide infra*). The residue, insoluble in sodium bicarbonate, was

crystallised from acetone, alcohol and other solvents when shining yellow needles, m.p. 185° (0.25 g.) could be obtained. (Found in a dry specimen: C, 61.68; H, 4.91; N, 6.58; OMe, 26.85. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$: C, 61.80; H, 4.72; N, 6.00; OMe, 26.61 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 205° (decomp.). (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 100°: N, 13.28. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{17}O_3N_3$: N, 13.0 per cent).

Isolation of γ -Fagaric Acid from the fraction (A) and (C).—The manganese dioxide residue and the sodium bicarbonate filtrate (C) (*vide supra*) were thoroughly digested with more sodium bicarbonate solution (aqueous) and filtered. The filtrate (50 c.c.) was cooled in ice, acidified with hydrochloric acid (congo red). The flocculent precipitate was collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. The colourless crystals (0.1 g.) melted at 215° (decomp.). (Found in a dry specimen: C, 57.53; H, 4.61; N 5.80; OMe, 24.68. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{11}O_3N$: C, 57.83; H, 4.41; N, 5.62; OMe, 24.89 per cent).

Decarboxylation of the Acid.—The acid (0.25 g.) was suspended in dilute hydrochloric acid (40 c.c., d. 1.15) and boiled till a clear solution resulted. On concentrating the solution (5 c.c.) colourless crystals separated, m. p. 248° (decomp.). On crystallisation from alcohol, the substance had the same m.p. (Found in a dry sample: C, 62.95; H, 4.88; N, 7.50. Calc. for $C_{10}H_9O_3N$: C, 62.82; H, 4.72; N, 7.33 per cent).

Nitroso derivative of the Decarboxylation Product.—The decarboxylation product (0.2 g.) was dissolved in alkali (2N) and the calculated amount of sodium nitrite was added to the solution. The solution, thus obtained, was added to a cooled solution of 10% sulphuric acid drop by drop. The reddish precipitate was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised repeatedly from acetic acid in red needles, m. p. 215° (decomp.). (Found in a [dry sample: N, 12.98. Calc. for $C_{10}H_8O_4N_2$: N, 12.72 per cent).

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